

Influence of Pressurizing Gases on Isothermal Decomposition Kinetics of Dibenzoyl Peroxide

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The effects of gases (C_2H_2 , N_2 , SO_2 and O_2) at different pressures on kinetic behaviour, maximum rates and induction periods of recrystallized dibenzoyl peroxide were studied. Kinetic results were interpreted by subsequent fittings of (i) contracting sphere equation, (ii) Jander equation and (iii) three-halves order equation, at different stages of decomposition. The reaction is of a surface type and the kinetic parameters were evaluated on the basis of diffusion of gaseous products of decomposition and pressurizing gases through condensed products matrix.

BENZOYL peroxide is fairly stable at room temperature but decomposes in solution at higher temperatures, yielding free radicals, and thus find applications as an initiator in polymerization reactions. The solventless decomposition of this substance is subject to several controversies. Decomposition at temperatures much below the normal melting point under one atmosphere of air¹ was interpreted on the basis of formation of an eutectic between condensed products and reactants leading to melting during decomposition. Pellets of about 20 mg mass were found to decompose isothermally, in high vacuum, near and above the normal melting point². However 40 mg pellets exploded above the melting point³ within induction periods of less than two minutes. Large charges of peroxide⁴, viz. 0.2 g, were found to explode, at temperatures much below the melting point, after extended self heating induction periods. The topochemical nature of decomposition of this peroxide was demonstrated in a previous study⁵, and the decomposition of purified peroxide was compared with that of the normal grade peroxide, the former being found to be much more stable than the latter. The action of impurity additives was investigated⁶, and it was

found that impurities have two effects, one due to mutual impurity and the other due to chemical interaction with benzoyloxy radicals formed initially upon decomposition.

This study was planned to investigate another topochemical factor which is the pressure change within ranges which does not normally influence reaction rates.

Experimental

Dibenzoyl peroxide supplied by Hopkins and Williams Ltd. was recrystallized by dissolving in cold chloroform⁷ and adding twice its volume of cold methanol. Crystals were washed with cold methanol and dried in vacuum at 40° for six hours. The apparatus consisted of a static vacuum system in which sample pellets of peroxide of the order of 30 mg mass were dropped into the reaction vessel by means of a glass spoon rotating around a ground glass joint. The reaction vessel was made of narrow tubing drawn at the end to facilitate heat-up time of peroxide samples.

Pressure measurements were performed by means of a differential recording manometer sensitive to ± 0.1 mm. Hg pressure difference⁸. The slow

decomposition was followed by taking manometer readings with the aid of a pye cathetometer. Temperature control was achieved by the use of Colara ultrathermostat sensitive to $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

The residual decomposition products were analysed by I. R. and thin layer chromatography. Decompositions were conducted in the temperature range 90° - 100° under gas pressures of 250, 500 and 695 torrs. Fractional decomposition was obtained by dividing pressure differences developed at different times during reaction by the final pressure difference at the end of the reaction.

Maximum rates were determined graphically from the maximum slopes of the fractional decomposition-time curves.

Results and Discussion

Fractional decomposition-time curves :

Enlarged fractional decomposition-time (α - t) curves in all cases show an initial gas evolution after a lapse of induction period. This period is then followed by another deceleratory period. Figure 1 shows the α - t curves for decomposition in oxygen.

Fig. 1 - Fractional decomposition time curves for Bz_2O_2 under 250 torrs of oxygen.

The kinetics is explained by fitting the curves into three equations as follows :

(1) The contracting sphere equation⁹ :

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{3}{2}} = K(t - t')$$

Where α = fractional decomposition,

t = time, and

t' = time of beginning of decomposition.

This equation was found to hold from the initial stages of decomposition till about 15% decomposition in most cases.

(2) The Jander equation¹⁰ :

$$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{3}{2}}]^2 = K(t - t')$$

This equation was found to fit the results in the range which follows the range fit of the contracting sphere equation and holds up till 50% decomposition.

(3) A three-halves order equation was found to fit the results from 50% till 90% of decomposition as follows :

$$\frac{1}{(p_f - p)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{1}{p_f^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{1}{2} Kt,$$

Where p_f = final pressure, and

p = pressure at time t .

Figures 2, 3 and 4 show fits of the three equations for the decomposition of recrystallized peroxide in presence of O_2 at pressure of 250 torrs.

Fig. 2 - Contracting sphere plots for first stage in decomposition of Bz_2O_2 under 250 torrs of oxygen.

Fig. 3 - Jander plots for second stage in decomposition of Bz_2O_2 under 250 torrs of oxygen.

Fig. 4—Three-halves order plots for decomposition of Bz_2O_2 under 250 torrs of oxygen.

Activation energies, induction periods and maximum rates :

Activation energies were found to be abnormally high. Table 1 shows the Arrhenius parameters obtained for the three equations.

The maximum rates determined from the maximum slopes of the α -t curves are given in Tables 2 and 3. Induction periods measured as the time to the maximum rates are given in Tables 4 and 5.

TABLE 1—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS

Pressures (Hg)	Contracting sphere		Jander equation		1.5 Order equation	
	Log A	E Kcal/mol	Log A	E Kcal/mol	Log A	E Kcal/mol
25 cm O_2	72.75	126.75	50.87	90.10	15.44	29.83
50 cm O_2	72.25	125.80	49.60	88.10	26.38	48.60
69.5 cm O_2	55.45	97.56	43.70	78.43	30.28	54.85
20 cm SO_2	—	—	33.39	61.01	12.48	24.96
50 cm SO_2	—	—	6.84	16.75	13.02	25.20
69.5 cm SO_2	—	—	2.80	9.94	14.24	27.96
25 cm C_2H_2	38.35	69.09	58.48	102.96	14.92	28.89
50 cm C_2H_2	55.52	98.06	58.10	102.27	21.13	39.33
69.5 cm C_2H_2	58.42	102.93	31.69	58.29	30.87	55.55
25 cm N_2	73.64	128.95	39.48	71.18	19.90	37.18
50 cm N_2	65.45	114.40	39.80	72.20	21.19	39.52
69.5 cm N_2	59.39	104.61	55.22	76.06	22.36	41.39

TABLE 2—MAXIMUM RATE ($MIN^{-1} \times 10^8$) FOR EFFECT OF O_2 AND SO_2

Temp. °C	O_2			SO_2		
	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.
100.0				52.17	27.52	12.98
97.5	50.01	43.10	39.62	12.14	10.20	9.76
95.0	23.58	22.26	15.92	10.28	7.24	6.60
92.5	11.58	10.16	8.42	9.01	7.03	6.31
90.0	6.84	5.16	3.35	7.74	6.50	5.85

TABLE 3—MAXIMUM RATE ($MIN^{-1} \times 10^{-8}$) FOR EFFECT OF C_2H_2 AND N_2

Temp. °C	C_2H_2			N_2		
	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.
100.0						
97.5	54.67	57.14	70.10	50.60	68.70	69.02
95.0	18.91	20.29	21.90	20.41	20.90	20.96
92.5	8.90	9.02	9.10	9.82	10.45	10.65
90.0	4.87	5.73	6.20	4.63	5.37	5.40

TABLE 4—INDUCTION PERIODS (MIN) FOR EFFECT OF O₂ AND SO₂

Temp. °C	O ₂			SO ₂		
	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.
100.0	22.0	21.9	21.5	48.2	44.7	42.3
97.5	42.0	39.8	37.4	63.0	46.7	43.9
95.0	83.8	82.4	79.2	198.2	190.6	190.4
92.5	198.0	185.0	179.2	370.0	361.6	276.6
90.0	376.0	350.0	328.5	776.2	568.6	503.0

TABLE 5—INDUCTION PERIODS (MIN.) FOR EFFECT OF C₂H₂ AND N₂

Temp. °C	C ₂ H ₂			N ₂		
	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.	25 cm. Hg.	50 cm. Hg.	69.5 cm. Hg.
100°0	17.5	16.3	14.5	18.7	16.5	16.0
97.5	40.5	36.5	33.8	45.5	39.5	37.2
95.0	116.8	91.5	87.0	117.0	96.8	96.4
92.5	255.6	217.5	212.2	261.2	228.4	213.8
90.0	588.4	483.4	432.0	591.2	489.6	466.6

Discussion

The decomposition of peroxides in dilute solutions was found to be governed by the rupture of the O-O bond which is the weakest bond in peroxide molecules. In case of solventless decomposition of dibenzoyl peroxide topochemical factors play a major role in its chemical stability. This was demonstrated by Morsi and Khalil for decomposition of commercial grade and purified grade benzoyl peroxide⁶.

Infrared spectra of residual decomposition products showed bands at 1690 and 1730 cm⁻¹ due to ν C=O of acid and ester respectively. Benzoic acid was detected by mixed melting point. The residual products contained yellow gummy material which is thought to be polymeric as evidenced by thin layer chromatography. These results are in agreement with those of Bowes¹ and Morsi and Khalil⁶.

Applicability of the contracting sphere equation and Jander equation for the first 50% of decomposition indicates that the decomposition starts on the surface and propagates through an interface. The surface reaction is evidenced in a microscopic study⁸ for the decomposition of single benzoyl crystals in which the decomposition started as surface streaks developing into cracks. During the later stages of reaction viz. after 50% decomposition the undecomposed reactants become suspended in the product matrix and thus conventional kinetic laws apply (three-halves order in this case).

Since the initial step is the scission of O-O bond, the subsequent steps follow from the reactivity of

benzoyloxy radicals. In this study the kinetic behaviour is explained on the basis of :

(i) Diffusion of carbon dioxide away from benzoyloxy radicals formed in the cage at the reaction interface.

(ii) Diffusion of pressurizing gas to the reaction interface and its subsequent physical and chemical interaction with benzoyloxy radicals at the interface.

The first is retarded both by increase of thickness of condensed product layer and by increase in pressure. The second is increased by pressure increase.

During the initial stages of decompositions, till the end of the range of fit of the contracting sphere equation, the diffusion of carbon dioxide, in condensed product layer, would not be rate determining since there is no well-defined interface. By simple calculation it can be shown that 20% surface change on spherical geometry occurs within only 7% of radius of a sphere provided no change in volume and no product loss by sublimation occur. Actually the product volume is expected to be smaller and also loss by sublimation is expected to occur.

For more than 20% decomposition the diffusion rate of CO₂ through the then well established product matrix should be taken into consideration. This explains the fitting of the Jander equation.

The very high activation energies obtained are due to the strong cage (solid state), in which decomposition is conducted. Such strong cage would reduce tremendously the radical mobilities thus enhancing thermal stabilities. Examples are the

persistence, over periods of months, of anisotropy in the esr spectra of organic crystals exposed to ionizing radiation¹¹⁻¹³.

For the later stages of decomposition of solids, 50-90%, it is common to apply conventional kinetic laws since the undecomposed reactants become suspended in the product matrix which rather resembles decomposition in solution.

The four gases were found to lower the values of induction periods. This is perhaps due to the decrease in heat-up time as a result of increased heat conduction by increase in pressure. The maximum rates increase by pressure increase in the case of acetylene and nitrogen, and this may be due to the increased instantaneous radical concentration as a result of decrease in radical mobilities with pressure increase. However, the maximum rates decrease with increased pressure of SO₂ and oxygen and this is due to coupling of SO₂ and O₂ with free radicals of reaction, since both compounds are paramagnetic.

Self heating is excluded in our case since it was found that tablets of comparable mass decompose isothermally in vacuum², also the rates in the four gases do not follow the thermal conductivity values. The thermal conductivities of the gases¹⁴ SO₂, C₂H₂, N₂ and O₂ in cal. sec⁻¹ cm⁻¹ deg⁻¹ are 2.27, 5.08, 6.24 and 6.35 respectively. If self-heating is

important, then decomposition in SO₂ should be fastest¹⁵ which is not the case.

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